

Fighting Spammers in Online Social Networks via Artificial Intelligence: Challenges and Solutions

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Online Social Networks (OSN) are Indispensable

Social Apps Used per Month

7.2

Daily Time Spend

2h 31m

Growing Spammers Pose Serious Threats to OSN

- Degrade the quality of user experience
 - Post spammy messages annoying users
- Steal sensitive information
 - Trick users to provide personal data
- Incur economic loss
 - 14 billion dollars loss per year (phishing, scam investment, deceptive information, etc.)
- Mislead users' political opinions

**How to effectively detect and remove spammers
remain opens!**

Challenges

- The social network contents are massive
 - *Lack effective data collection mechanism*
- Spammers can post both spammy messages and images
 - *Such multi-model data are hard to be processed through a uniform classification model*
- The spammers contents only occupy a small portion
 - *Belong to the imbalance classification problem (spam contents take only 10%-20% percentage)*
 - *The normal contents dominate the training process, overwhelming the minority class's patterns*

Our Goals

- Develop an effective data collection mechanism
 - Elastic-honeypot: maintain a dynamic set of normal users to serve as honeypot
 - Collecting network contents that have the high potential of including spam messages
- Develop a novel solution for spam messages classification
 - Expose spam messages' outlier property for classification
- Develop a novel solution for spam images classification
 - Downsample the normal image class (majority) while preserving valuable information

Elastic-honeypot: Dynamic Honeypot Selection Mechanism

Honeypot-based Solutions

- Create artificial honeypot users for attracting spammers
- Honeypot users have certain features attracting spammers' interests
- Monitor honeypots users' contents for spammer detection
- Disguise itself as an ordinary user account to capture spammers
- **Advantages**
 - Low data collection and computation overhead
 - High spammer detection rate
- **Limitations**
 - *High deployment overhead*: Honeypot account needs to be set up manually
 - *Unscalable*: hard to create many honeypot accounts
 - *Limited attribute settings*: It is difficult to create an account with the 10-year age
 - *Limited efficiency*: Few detected spammers due to small number of honeypot accounts

Our Solution: Elastic-honeypot

- Instead of manually creating honeypot accounts for spammer detection, we maintain a dynamic subset of normal users to serve as honeypot
 - Take advantage of users diversity to select normal users most attractive to spammers
 - Dynamically adjust honeypot users
- Monitor their received tweets for spammer detection
- **Advantages**
 - *Low deployment overhead*
 - *More flexible attribute settings*
 - *High scalability*
 - *High efficiency*

Challenges

- How to select honeypot users that can effectively attract spammers?
 - A huge amount of users in OSNs
- How to maintain honeypot efficiency through dynamic adjusting?
 - Inactive users will lose spammer's interests

Which Users to Select?

- Select users with attributes attractive to spammers
 - Those users received most spam messages
- Gradually learn attributes that are more attractive to spammers
 - Number of friends, account age, status count, trending-up topic, business hashtag, etc.
- We dynamically select these accounts to serve as our honeypot

Honeypot Selection based on Attributes: How?

- The most effective attributes

Continuous Refinement through Feedback Loop

Deployment via Streaming API

Dynamic Honeypot Adjustment

- Dynamically adjust honeypot users by removing dormant users and adding active users

Active elastic-honeypot node

Dormant elastic-honeypot node

Implementation and Experiments on Twitter

- Select honeypot users based on 24 attributes
 - Trending-based attributes
 - Top 10 topics under each attribute
 - 10 accounts for each topic
 - Profile-based attributes
 - 10 accounts for each sampled attribute value
 - Hashtag-based attributes
 - 100 accounts for each attribute
- Maintain 2400 honeypot users, updated once every hour
- Run the elastic-honeypot for 700 hours

Classification

- We label data collected in the first 100 hours
 - 19,296 spams and 6,096 spammers
 - 20,000 non-spams
- We apply the machine learning for spam classification
- In our 700-hour experiments
 - We collect 5.6M tweets from 2.7M users
 - Among them, we detect a total of 1.2M spam tweets and 50,966 spammers

Performance Comparison

- 100-hour experiment from 100 honeypot users

Elastic-honeypot v.s. Honeypot-based methods

Honeypot method	Time	Running duration	# of honeypots	# of spams	# of spammers	PGE
Stringhini <i>et.al.</i> [27]	2010	11 months	300	–	15,857	0.0067
Lee <i>et.al.</i> [17]	2011	7 month	60	–	36,000	0.12
Yang <i>et.al.</i> [38]	2014	5 month	96	17,000	1,159	0.0034
Yang <i>et.al.</i> [38]’s advanced system	2014	10 days	10	–	–	0.087
Elastic-honeypot	2018	100 hours	100	339,553	17,336	1.7336

Drawbacks in Traditional Supervised Learning

- Supervised learning typically requires a large and balanced ground truth dataset

Drawbacks

Labor-intensive

Effective feature
extraction

Time-consuming

Spam feature drift issue

Error-prone

Label 19, 296 spams and 20,000 non-spams

One student takes one
month for labeling!!!

**Labeling a balanced and large-sized ground truth dataset
remain challenging!**

Imbalanced Classification for Spam Messages via Exposing Outlier Property

Our Observation

Spam tweets typically contain more URLs than benign tweets, causing them to stand out.

Spam tweets exhibit distinct features across different attributes

- Two observations
 - Spammers' patterns tend to exhibit as outlier: drawing in red colors
 - Simply apply attributes statistics not enough: Spammers disguise themselves within normal users, making their patterns inapparent

Our Idea

- We develop an unsupervised approach to expose the disparity between spam and non-spam messages
 - Explore the specific syntaxes and semantics of spam and non-spam messages
 - Encode each message into a vector of score, representing its patterns
- Apply the outlier detection techniques to detect spam messages
 - Rank all messages
 - The spam messages will stand out: expecting to have higher ranks than non-spam messages, considered as the outlier
 - Directly remove the messages appearing at the outliers

Find the Occurrence of N-grams

- For a set of collected tweets, we find the stem words and split to N-grams
- Then, we compute the occurrence of N-grams

ABC

message m_1

AB

message m_2

BC

message m_3

DEF

message m_4

A, B, C, D, E, F are stem words

Split to N-grams

$$Sub_T = \{A, B, C, D, E, F, AB, BC, DE, EF, ABC, DEF\}$$

Occurrence Checking

$$Occ(A) = Occ(AB) = \{m_1, m_2\}$$

$$Occ(C) = Occ(BC) = \{m_1, m_3\}$$

$$Occ(D) = Occ(E) = Occ(F)$$

$$= Occ(DE) = Occ(EF) = Occ(DEF) = \{m_4\}$$

$$Occ(B) = \{m_1, m_2, m_3\}$$

$$Occ(ABC) = \{m_1\}$$

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ABC ← message m_1

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$$Occ(B) = \{m_1, m_2, m_3\}$$

$$Occ(ABC) = \{m_1\}$$

Find the Occurrence of N-grams

- For a set of collected tweets, we find the stem words and split to N-grams
- Then, we compute the occurrence of N-grams

A, B, C, D, E, F are stem words

Split to N-grams

$$Sub_T = \{A, B, C, D, E, F, AB, BC, DE, EF, ABC, DEF\}$$

Occurrence Checking

$$Occ(A) = Occ(AB) = \{m_1, m_2\} \quad \text{A and AB are equivalent structures}$$

$$Occ(C) = Occ(BC) = \{m_1, m_3\}$$

$$Occ(D) = Occ(E) = Occ(F)$$

$$= Occ(DE) = Occ(EF) = Occ(DEF) = \{m_4\}$$

$$Occ(B) = \{m_1, m_2, m_3\}$$

$$Occ(ABC) = \{m_1\}$$

Find the Common and Uncommon Patterns

- Two metrics are used to define the common and uncommon patterns
 - Average Longest Equivalent Relation (ALER): uncommon pattern
 - Mass Class Equivalent Relation (MCER): common pattern

	Split to N-grams		ALER	MCER
ABC m_1	$Sub_T = \{A, B, C, D, E, F, AB, BC, DE, EF, ABC, DEF\}$	A, B, C, AB, BC, ABC	$(2+1+2+2+2+3)/6 = 2$	4
		$A_{Occ}, B_{Occ}, C_{Occ}, ABC_{Occ}$		
AB m_2	Find Equivalent Grams $Occ(A) \equiv Occ(AB)$ $Occ(C) \equiv Occ(BC)$ $Occ(D) \equiv Occ(E) \equiv Occ(F)$ $\equiv Occ(DE) \equiv Occ(EF)$ $\equiv Occ(DEF)$	A, B, AB	$(2+1+2)/3 = 1.7$	2
		A_{Occ}, B_{Occ}		
BC m_3		B, C, BC	$(2+1+2)/3 = 1.7$	2
		B_{Occ}, C_{Occ}		
DEF m_4		D, E, F, DE, EF, DEF	$(3*6)/3 = 3$	1
		D_{Occ}		

Seed Collection

- **Spam seed:** the stem words in the top 1% ALER messages, but not appearing in the top 1% MCER messages
- **Non-spam seed:** the stem words in the top 1% MCER messages, but not appearing in the top 1% ALER messages

Initialize Labels

- Initialize all tweets' labels based on spam seed and non-spam seed
- Four cases

A tweet only contains spam words

Spam

A tweet only contains non-spam words

Non-spam

A tweet contains both spam and non-spam words

- **Non-spam**: If the number of non-spam words is greater than spam words
- **Spam**: Otherwise

No seed word is contained in a tweet

Random label

Initialize Word Distribution

- Compute frequency of each word in both non-spam tweets and spam tweets

Iteratively Recompute Label for Each Tweet

- Based on word distributions, we iteratively recompute the label of each tweet
- In each iteration
 - We randomly pick up one tweet
 - Recalculate the word frequency by removing this tweet from the corresponding dataset
 - Calculate the probability of this messages to be spam or non-spam based on its stem words distribution
 - Add this tweet back to corresponding dataset
- We terminate such a processing until the word distributions in both spam and non-spam datasets converge

Calculating Word Spam Score

- In each iteration, we save each word's frequencies $\theta_1^{(k)}$ and $\theta_0^{(k)}$ in spam dataset and non-spam dataset, respectively
- Each word's spam score can be calculated by

$$s_i = \frac{1}{K} \sum_k \frac{\theta_1^{(k)}(i)}{\theta_1^{(k)}(i) + \theta_0^{(k)}(i)}$$

s_i : Spam score for word w_i .
 k : k-th iteration.
 K : total number of iterations.

- We construct the spam and non-spam word corpus based on thresholds

Train a Deep Learning Model

- For each word, we use NLP model (i.e., GloVe) to convert into the high-dimensional vector
- All words' vectors and their scores are to train a deep learning model

Generating Spam Vector

- For each tweet, we extract all stem words and employ the trained model to predict their spam scores

Magnitude Outlier

- For each spam vector, we compute its magnitude index
- We then sort all magnitude indices

Unsupervised Scalable Statistical Method for Identifying Influential Users in Online Social Networks. *Scientific Reports*, 8(1):6955, 2018.

Performance

Twitter Trending

Twitter Normal

Information-perservable Undersampling Approach for Imbalanced Image Classification

Majority-biased Boundary for Imbalanced Data

Balanced Boundary

Majority-biased Boundary

Our Solution

- Existing Undersampling Methods [He, TKDE'09; Liu, TSMC'09; Yin, AAAI'20]
 - Discard a vast amount of majority instances for balancing the dataset
 - **Limitation:** incur significant information loss
- We develop a novel undersampling approach to balance the dataset
 - Computational efficient
 - Information preservable
- We divide the training into a two-stage operation
 - *Representation learning*: learn meaningful and diverse latent representations
 - *Balancing*: discard the majority samples to rectify the decision boundary

Representation Learning

- We propose a cascade variational auto-encoder (VAE) to learn the rich patterns
 - Compress high-dimensional images to low-dimensional latent factors to reduce the computational cost
 - Learn meaningful and diverse latent representations

Representation Learning

- We consider two types of Bayesian Networks

Non-hierarchical structure $p_{\mathcal{B}}(\hat{\mathbf{z}}) = \prod_{j=1}^d p(\hat{z}_j | z_j)$

Hierarchical Structure $p_{\mathcal{B}}(\hat{\mathbf{z}}) = \prod_{j=1}^d p(\hat{z}_j | Pa(\hat{z}_j))$
e.g., $p(\hat{z}_3 | Pa(\hat{z}_3)) = p(\hat{z}_3 | z_3, \hat{z}_1, \hat{z}_2)$

- Our cascade VAE can
 - Learn the hierarchical patterns, enhancing the reconstructing quality
 - Learn the meaningful and diverse patterns
 - Compress the high-dimensional image into low-dimensional latent vector

Undersampling the Dataset

- For each data sample, we input to the encoder to get the latent vector

- We calculate the similarity matrix between any two latent vectors

$$\mathbf{L} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \text{sim}(\mathbf{z}^{(1)}, \mathbf{z}^{(2)}) & \dots & \text{sim}(\mathbf{z}^{(1)}, \mathbf{z}^{(n)}) \\ \text{sim}(\mathbf{z}^{(2)}, \mathbf{z}^{(1)}) & 1 & \dots & \text{sim}(\mathbf{z}^{(2)}, \mathbf{z}^{(n)}) \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \text{sim}(\mathbf{z}^{(n)}, \mathbf{z}^{(1)}) & \text{sim}(\mathbf{z}^{(n)}, \mathbf{z}^{(2)}) & \dots & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

Undersampling: Determinantal Point Process

- We resort to the Determinantal Point Process (DPP) to sample a subset of diverse samples from the majority class data
 - Given a dataset Y with N items, a point process \mathcal{P} in this set is a distribution over discrete and finite subsets of Y . Consider a symmetric kernel matrix $\mathbf{K} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times N}$, a DPP, for any subset $S \subseteq Y$, is defined as:

$$\mathcal{P}(S) = \det(\mathbf{K}_S)$$

- \mathcal{P} is a probability measurement and \mathbf{K}_S is a principle submatrix of \mathbf{K} .
- For example, assume a dataset $Y = \{1, 2, 3\}$ with the kernel matrix $\mathbf{K} = \begin{vmatrix} K_{11} & K_{12} & K_{13} \\ K_{21} & K_{22} & K_{23} \\ K_{31} & K_{32} & K_{33} \end{vmatrix}$

$$\mathcal{P}(\{1, 2\}) = \det\left(\begin{vmatrix} K_{11} & K_{12} \\ K_{21} & K_{22} \end{vmatrix}\right) = K_{11} \cdot K_{22} - K_{12} \cdot K_{21}$$

$$\mathcal{P}(\{1, 3\}) = \det\left(\begin{vmatrix} K_{11} & K_{13} \\ K_{31} & K_{33} \end{vmatrix}\right) = K_{11} \cdot K_{33} - K_{13} \cdot K_{31}$$

$$\mathcal{P}(\{2, 3\}) = \det\left(\begin{vmatrix} K_{22} & K_{23} \\ K_{32} & K_{33} \end{vmatrix}\right) = K_{22} \cdot K_{33} - K_{23} \cdot K_{32}$$

Undersampling: DPP with L-ensemble

- However, since \mathcal{P} is a probability measurement, *i.e.*, $0 \leq \mathcal{P} \leq 1$, \mathbf{K} must satisfy two conditions:
 - Positive semidefinite
 - All eigenvalues of \mathbf{K} are less than or equal to 1
- It is difficult to construct DPP through \mathbf{K} in real scenarios. Instead, we adopt L-ensemble

$$\mathcal{P}_{\mathbf{L}}(S) = \frac{\det(\mathbf{L}_S)}{\det(\mathbf{L} + \mathbf{I})} \propto \det(\mathbf{L}_S)$$

- where \mathbf{I} is an identity matrix and \mathbf{L} is a positive semidefinite kernel matrix, \mathcal{P} naturally satisfies $0 \leq \mathcal{P} \leq 1$
- \mathbf{L} employs the similarity matrix

$$\mathbf{L} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \text{sim}(\mathbf{z}^{(1)}, \mathbf{z}^{(2)}) & \cdots & \text{sim}(\mathbf{z}^{(1)}, \mathbf{z}^{(n)}) \\ \text{sim}(\mathbf{z}^{(2)}, \mathbf{z}^{(1)}) & 1 & \cdots & \text{sim}(\mathbf{z}^{(2)}, \mathbf{z}^{(n)}) \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \text{sim}(\mathbf{z}^{(n)}, \mathbf{z}^{(1)}) & \text{sim}(\mathbf{z}^{(n)}, \mathbf{z}^{(2)}) & \cdots & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

Diversity Property

- An example

- For $Y=\{1, 2, 3\}$, two-element subsets include $\{(1, 2), (2, 3), (1, 3)\}$, for each S

$$\mathcal{P}(\{i, j\}) = \det\left(\begin{array}{cc} \mathbf{K}_{ii} & \mathbf{K}_{ij} \\ \mathbf{K}_{ji} & \mathbf{K}_{jj} \end{array}\right) = \mathbf{K}_{ii}\mathbf{K}_{jj} - \mathbf{K}_{ij}\mathbf{K}_{ji} = \mathcal{P}(\{i\})\mathcal{P}(\{j\}) - \mathbf{K}_{ij}^2$$

- Correspondingly, for DPP with \mathbf{L} -ensemble, we have

$$\mathcal{P}_{\mathbf{L}}(\{i, j\}) \propto \mathcal{P}_{\mathbf{L}}(\{i\})\mathcal{P}_{\mathbf{L}}(\{j\}) - \left(\frac{\mathbf{L}_{ij}}{\det(\mathbf{L} + \mathbf{I})}\right)^2$$

$$\mathcal{P}_{\mathbf{L}}(\{i, j\}) \propto -\mathbf{L}_{ij}^2 = -(\text{sim}(i, j))^2$$

- The higher similarity between item i and item j , the less likely they are sampled simultaneously
 - ✓ The sample data have the high diversity

Experimental Results: Diverse Latent Representations

- Decompose a high-order latent feature into three disentangled ones

- Synthesize a high-order latent feature from two disentangled ones

Experimental Results: Performance on Imbalanced data

- Experimental Settings:
 - Models: LeNet for MNIST and VGG-16 for CIFAR-10
 - Baselines: undersampling, oversampling, and re-weighting
 - Many-shot: 4000, 2000, 1000, and 750 samples
 - Medium-shot: 500, 350, 200, and 100 samples
 - Few-shot: 60 and 40 samples

Methods		MNIST				CIFAR-10			
		Many	Medium	Few	Overall	Many	Medium	Few	Overall
Undersampling	Random	92.3	89.3	81.6	89.1	77.9	72.4	69.4	74.5
Oversampling	GAMO	95.0	85.6	89.4	89.4	78.5	78.4	73.2	78.1
	DGC	92.2	91.0	97.9	92.3	77.2	78.5	81.2	78.6
	IMSIC	94.3	92.2	98.0	94.0	81.1	80.6	81.2	80.7
Re-weighting	Focal Loss	90.9	93.3	94.3	92.7	81.1	83.2	76.2	81.1
	CB Loss	94.0	93.5	95.6	94.2	81.2	83.9	82.6	82.6
	LDAM	94.7	91.6	96.8	93.7	82.1	84.7	78.5	82.5
	Logit Adjustment	96.2	95.7	94.0	95.6	83.6	85.2	82.8	84.1
	PaCo Loss	96.3	95.9	91.5	95.2	81.8	84.1	82.8	83.0
Two-stage	LDAM-DRW	92.9	95.9	96.4	94.7	82.0	83.9	83.9	83.1
	Decouple (τ -norm)	96.6	95.9	94.2	95.9	84.1	86.1	80.0	84.2
Ours (k-DPP)		96.5	96.8	98.0	96.9	87.8	87.6	90.1	88.2
Balanced		-	-	-	97.3	-	-	-	92.6

Compared to accuracies on balanced datasets, our approach achieves marginal performance degradation, i.e., 0.4% on MNIST and 4.4% on CIFAR-10.

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Recomputing Label for Each tweet

Sample one message

1 Remove all related records about m_j

2 Relabel m_j

3 Add back m_j with new label

Example

ABC message m_1

AB message m_2

DEF message m_4

	A	B	C	D	E	F
θ_0	3	3	2	1	1	1
θ_1	1	1	1	2	2	2

BC message m_3

$$Pr(L(m_3) = 0) = \frac{3 * 2}{3 * 2 + 1 * 1} = 0.86$$

$$Pr(L(m_3) = 1) = \frac{1 * 1}{1 * 1 + 3 * 2} = 0.14$$

State-of-The-Arts

- Oversampling Methods [Chawla, JAIR'02; Ojha, NeurIPS'20; He, IJCAI'21]
 - Balance the class priors through synthesizing the data of minority classes
 - **Limitation:** heavy computational overhead and incurring overfitting
- Re-weighting Methods [Lin, ICCV'17; Cao, NeurIPS'19; Menon, ICLR'21]
 - Prevent samples of majority classes dominating the training by down-weighting their loss
 - **Limitation:** heuristic; require domain expertise to craft task-specific loss functions

Conventional Methods

Oversampling Methods

Re-weighting Methods